

BOOK REVIEW

A Review of *Beads of Arunachal Pradesh: Emerging Cultural Context*

Sarit Kumar Chaudhuri and Sucheta Sen Chaudhuri

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In *Beads of Arunachal Pradesh: Emerging Cultural Context*, published by the Niyogi Books, New Delhi, in collaboration with Maulana Kalam Azad Institute of Asian Studies, Kolkata, authors Sarit Kumar Chaudhuri and Sucheta Sen Chaudhuri introduce the significance of beads in the tribal life and culture of Northeast India in general and Arunachal Pradesh in particular. This book, they assert, reveals the process of negotiation in the domain of tangible culture, which is deeply embedded in the intangible cultural heritage of the people and linked with wider socio-political processes, which regulate everyday nuances of people's life (p. 9). The Northeast, particularly Arunachal Pradesh, accords a special place for beads in its cultural milieu. The state's geo-political location, with 26 major and several smaller tribes and their innumerable migration stories, adds a new dimension to the tradition of beads.

The authors have made extensive use of both primary and secondary sources of data as is evident from their exhaustive references as well as their personal fieldwork among the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh. The book describes the economic, cultural, and ritual significance of beads, their historical relation to migration and popular beliefs, classification mechanism, legends and history around them, and ethnic specifications. Notwithstanding the impact of globalization, the popularity of beads among the tribal societies has not diminished even in rural areas. Beads are still used as a bartering item in remote places where the modern economic system has hardly reached. Beads are a status symbol among the state's tribal societies.

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The book comprises seven chapters besides a preface, bibliography, acknowledgements, and index. In the introductory chapter, authors give a brief historical background of the beads culture in some parts of Africa where beads were fashioned from ostrich egg shells as early as 10,000 BCE, especially in Libya and Sudan, and their association with the prayer tradition of major religions of the world—Hinduism, Buddhism, Christianity, and Islam (p.11). Alongside, the authors discuss the following research problems of their study in this chapter: (a) how do people desire to beautify the body and how does one account for differences in adornment and attire, based on gender and their changes through time and space?; (b) what are the traditional economic, cultural, and ritual significance of beads?; (c) how are beads historically related to migration and what are the routes and mechanisms of trade involved with beads?; (d) what are the popular beliefs, classification mechanism, and ethnic specificities of various beads?; and (e) how are beads understood and redefined by Arunachal tribes in the changing cultural as well as socio-political context? (p. 20).

In the second chapter, the authors discuss the diversity of beads and ornaments among various tribes of Arunachal Pradesh. The aspects covered are – beads as status symbol and identity, ritualistic significance of beads, beads as a commodity, and beads among younger generations. According to the authors, beads are worn also to mark the wearer's social and cultural status during festivals, cultural events, and even at the reception of important people. The role of beads as an identity has become more important with increase in ethnic aspirations. In this age of globalization, global events influence even the remotest area. Fashion shows are spreading fast. Beads are displayed here, elaborately showcasing their ethnic identity and aesthetic sensibilities (p. 24). The authors also make a comparative analysis of the range of prices for different beads of the Arunachal tribes.

A vivid account of folklores, myths, and legends of the origin of beads among different tribal groups of Arunachal Pradesh is the focus of the third chapter. An attempt has also been made by the authors to describe the legends as well as the historical reconstruction of beads trade, migration of beads, and related issues based on both oral and literary sources. Beads are part of the oral tradition of every tribe. Beads reveal their historic linkages across the political and cultural boundaries through trade, economic status of an individual in a society, as well as being the medium of exchange. They obviously help identify the tribe to a great extent (p. 15).

In the fourth chapter, the authors deal with gender variation, especially in relation to the question of inheritance of various beads, necklaces or ornaments. Herein the authors focus on some ethnographic writings on beads and gender, gender specifications of beads in Arunachal tribes, and inheritance of beads among tribes. In most tribes, observe the authors, there is a distinct gender variation in using beads for personal adornment. A few beads are, however, used by both male and female members. Largely, beads are related to women and are important items of exchange during marriage. Even today, original beads are considered highly-valued movable property which, by and large, is inherited through the female line. Most tribes are guided by their customary laws where we find small variations from tribe to tribe in such laws of inheritance.

Chapter five highlights the emerging realities of beads culture among Arunachal tribes. The authors argue that beads, being one of the most valued possessions of the people, are a source of their livelihood (p. 121). Young people's perception of beads and beads trade as a mode of income and livelihood are highlighted by the authors. Drawing an example from young and educated Nyishis of Daporijo area, the authors point out that young, even educated Nyishis, do not have fair idea on the different types of beads used by their community members (p. 122). However, it has been noted that politicians of all ages keep buying as many beads as possible since the beads carry high traditional value. With change in times, beads, too, have undergone a lot of changes. Innovative beads with comparable texture and colour are penetrating the bead market. Beads with entirely new shapes, sizes, and colours, which were unknown to the people, are also found in the bead markets. With regard to their trade, the authors note that most of the bead traders are tribal women belong to Nyishi, Apatani, and Adi tribes who buy new beads with similar texture and colour of the traditional beads from Harmuti and Lakhimpur markets of neighbouring State of Assam where they have their own production units (p. 125). Noting that there is a strong perception of fake and original beads among the tribes, most tribes have people, generally the elderly, who can distinguish between the two varieties. This differentiation is very important as it has a direct relation with their pricing. The originals are old beads which the community acquired through trade or obtained from countries such as Tibet, Burma, Bhutan, and China. These could also have been obtained from the plains of Assam by trade or bartering with local products of hill tribes.

In the penultimate chapter, the authors illustrate the beliefs, utility, and values of beads in tribal societies of Arunachal Pradesh. In particular, they seek to understand the religious values of beads, taboos associated with beads, beads as symbol of high social status, and beads as identity markers. The book notes that at all levels of society, possession of beads is of tremendous importance as it is associated with individuals as well as group identity. In terms of its religious values, beads are used during rituals such as births and deaths, as well as other occasions such as for curing ailments (p. 134). With regard to beads as symbol of high social status, those with large number of beads are respected by the villagers and communities; the credit of such honour goes to the entire clan as well (p. 135).

In the concluding chapter, the authors subsume the foregoing discussions of the book to understand the linkages between material elements in terms of beads and ornaments and their social and cultural values among tribes of Arunachal Pradesh (p. 141). They note that the concept of fashion show is becoming integral to the state, cutting across communities or cultural boundaries. In contemporary Arunachal Pradesh, while celebrating tribe-specific popular festivals, one can see such fashion shows or walking the ramp across the rural-urban divide, especially among the younger generation. This has created a huge new cultural domain where traditional costumes, especially textiles and bead ornaments, have received a new meaning in the form of innovative designs while most tribes try to maintain their tribe-specific identity markers by using tribal motifs or wearing traditional bead ornaments or even using other forms of traditional body arts such as tattoos (p. 144). Having said this, personal adornment and use of beads and other ornaments reflect exceptional aesthetic wits of the tribals of Arunachal Pradesh.

This book is a useful, up-to-date, and authoritative compilation of ground level knowledge on the past trends, present status, and future prospects of beads in tribal cultures of Arunachal Pradesh. The book is undoubtedly an anthropologist's delight but there is much for the lay person too in its plethora of images. To that extent, the painstakingly-researched *Beads of Arunachal Pradesh: Emerging Cultural Context* is one for scholar's collection and serves as a definitive work on the customs and traditions of an academically less-explored north-eastern state about which little is known outside the region.